

Influence of Work Environment on Library Staff Job Performance in State University Libraries, North-East, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Background: This study investigated the influence of the work environment on the job performance of library staff in six state university libraries in North-East, Nigeria. The objectives were to determine the level of library staff job performance, assess the conduciveness of the work environment, and evaluate the influence of the work environment on job performance.

Method: A survey research design was adopted, targeting professional and para-professional library staff in three selected state university libraries in North-East, Nigeria. A census sampling technique was used due to the manageable population size. Data were collected using a self-developed questionnaire titled “Questionnaire on Influence of Work Environment on Library Staff Job Performance in State University Libraries, North-East, Nigeria” (QWJP). Descriptive statistics were used for analysis, and linear regression was applied to test the influence of the work environment (independent variable) on job performance (dependent variable).

Findings/Results: The analysis revealed a moderate level of job performance among library staff (descriptive statistics). The work environment was found to be highly conducive. Linear regression results indicated a statistically significant influence of the work environment on job performance of library staff in the state university libraries ($p < 0.05$).

Implications: The findings suggest that a conducive work environment significantly enhances the job performance of library staff, highlighting the importance of maintaining supportive workplace conditions to improve staff productivity and efficiency.

Conclusion: The study concludes that the work environment significantly influences the job performance of library staff in state university libraries in North-East, Nigeria, with a conducive environment being a key factor in achieving better performance outcomes.

Recommendations: The study recommends that library management in the studied institutions should prioritize sustaining a conducive work environment to elevate library staff job performance from moderate to high levels.

Keywords: Work Environment, Job performance, Library Staff, University Libraries

INTRODUCTION

Work environment plays a crucial role on employees’ efforts toward achieving their mandate in any type of organization. Work Environment is considered one of the factors that can determine employees’ performance in their effort to achieve organizational goal. The work environment is a composite of three major sub-environments: the technical environment, the human environment and the organizational environment (Opperman, 2002) in Pandey (2023). Agada and Tofi (2020) listed four types of work environment. These are: the physical, social, psychological and technological. The physical work environment is concerned with tools, equipment/infrastructure needed to enhance the work place. Technical environment refers to technological infrastructure. The psychological work environment has to do with cordial

relationship with co-workers and spirit of team work. There is also human environment which refers to peers, others with whom employees relates such as team and work groups as well as the leadership and management of the organization. (Onuoha, Okwanga & Otuza, 2020).

A broader classification of work environment is: the physical and the non-Physical work environment (Sadarmayanti in Fithri et al. (2019). The physical work environment (PWE) according to them are the conditions that are around the work place and can affect employee's performance both directly and indirectly. The PWE includes lighting, furniture, office design, temperature, ventilation, noise level and space (Adetayo, Adeleleke & Lateef, 2023). The non-physical work environment entails relationship with supervisors, peers with whom employees relates, team and work groups, interactional issues such as communication and knowledge sharing behaviour among employees. Others are: the leadership and management.

The library staff perform different jobs that are technical, administrative and advisory in nature. The technical duties have to do with the selection, acquisition, organization, and dissemination of information resources in prints and non-prints. The advisory task of librarian may involve all the activities of reference and information services such as selective dissemination of information (SDI), current awareness services (CAS), user education/user orientation. Other duties of the library staff are information literacy instruction; computer and ICT training; coordination with community groups to host public services (Onuoha, Ukangwa & Otuza, 2020). These activities ensure timely and efficient access to physical and digital resources in supporting research and academic activities. Therefore, the jobs require a degree of effectiveness, resulting into appreciable level of job performance.

The library staff job performance is crucial to the success of the libraries and that of their founding institutions. Job performance is the results or outcome and that aspect of work behaviour(s) that is of relevance to the library's success. The behaviours expected from a library staff are punctuality, being effective and timely in doing their task. Performing the tasks and duties assigned assigned to them at the expected time through effective and efficient manner are the performance indicators of the staff's job performance (Ikonne & Fajoyonmi, 2019). In the library context, job performance indicators include technical performance proficiency, job knowledge, job skill and job output (Eyo, 2021).

It is a common knowledge that environment shapes human attitude, therefore, Shammout (2021) asserts that humans are affected by both physical and non-physical surroundings. The environment in which a job is performed is an important factor that determines the level of employees' performance (Atanda & Udoedouok, 2020). Consequently, work environment can shape library staff attitudes toward the jobs they perform. Employees put in more effort to perform better when the immediate environment condition corresponds with their obligation. A positive attitude towards work by library staff will result in appreciable level of job performance. Infrastructure made available to the library personnel enable them to achieve a large amount of work in small time. The physical work environment has an impact on the level and nature of social interaction between co-workers thereby influencing the social working environment. In other word, the physical layout may determine the kinds of interactions that can take place within a work environment (Akinlade et al., 2022). On the other side, unconducive work environment associated with poor lighting, poor ventilation, congested work space and lack of cooperation and support can bring about a serious failure to organization like libraries.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The job performance of the library staff towards supporting the mandate of state universities, is crucial. This is because the job performance of the library staff help to achieve the libraries' objectives and that of their parent bodies teaching, learning and research through the provision of effective information services. For the library staff to put in their best towards the jobs they do, the libraries management have to provide a conducive work environment characterized by comfortable furniture, adequate ventilation and tools to work with which results into an appreciable level of job performance.

Preliminary investigation through interaction with some of the library staff in the libraries under study have shown that the level of job performance of the library staff appears to be low, despite the importance of tasks undertaken by them to attain library goals and objectives and that of the founding institutions (state universities in North-east, Nigeria). The researcher's observations have also shown that, the work environment in the libraries under study, seems to be in contrast with the ideal situation. This is a problem when one considers the strong need for a conducive work environment in realizing a good level of performance. The concern is that could the observed level of job performance be as a result of the condition of the work environment or due to something else?

Furthermore, empirical studies on work environment and job performance of library staff have been conducted in states and federal University libraries in other geo-political zones of Nigeria. However similar study seems to be lacking in state university libraries, north-east, Nigeria. This study therefore intended to fill the existing gap by investigating the level of job performance, level of conduciveness of their work environment and whether work environment influences the job performance of library staff in state university libraries, North-east, Nigeria.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. What is the level of library staff job performance in the state university libraries, north-east, Nigeria.
2. What is the level of conduciveness of work environment of library staff in the state university libraries, north-east, Nigeria.

RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

Ho There is no significant influence of work environment on library staff job performance in state universities libraries, north-east, Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The job performance of employees is paramount to the organization's success like the libraries. Therefore given attention to that should not be under estimated. In a study by Eyo (2021) on work environment, staff development and personnel variables and job performance of Library personnel in Public Universities in the South-south, Nigeria, a survey design was adopted by through questionnaire. The research data were collected from 762 professional library staff and were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The results unveiled that Fabunmi et al. (2023) studied Staff training as Determinant of Job performance of Librarians in Public Universities in Southern Nigeria. The results unveiled that, the level of job performance of librarians was high. Verma and Singh (2019) in a study of Level of Job Performance of Library professionals in University Libraries in Varanasi India based on Gender and Work experience through a survey method. Data were gathered from thirty-eight

(83) library professionals. The findings of the study revealed an average level of Job Performance. Contrary to the above findings, is that of Ikonne and Fajoyonmi (2019) who studied Work environment of Academic Librarians in Federal University libraries North-east, Nigeria. Questionnaire was used to collect data from 275 librarians and the data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Results, revealed that librarians' performance in the study area is low and is due to poor illumination in the work place. In corroboration of the above finding, is an observation by Saidat and Sunmade (2019) that, inadequate infrastructural facilities, poor technological skill are some of the problems hindering performance among the library staff in the library under study.

The work environment is critical to employees' performance and satisfaction. Sikowo et al. (2016) investigated Determinants of Employees' Satisfaction on Organizational performance at Trans Nzoia County Government'. The results indicated that work space, work tools and resources like stationary, computers, and internet are insufficient. They expressed that work space allows the worker to move freely in or around work place. A restricted movement may have psychological effect on an individual worker resulting in low job performance. Agada and Tofi (2020) investigated the Influence of Works environment and Staff training on Job performance of Library staff in University libraries in Nasarawa state. Results revealed that, conducive work environment is indicated by comfortable office, constant power and spacious office influence job performance. Others are absent of pressure and adequate lighting. Similarly, Adetayo et al. (2023) in their study titled 'Does the physical work environment of Librarians influence research productivity' hold the opinion that, the work environment of Librarians in their study area is conducive by having a good light, comfortable office, a clean and noiseless environment. Contrary to the above findings was that of Oyrinde (2020) whose study was on leadership style, work environment, organizational silence and institution effectiveness. A survey research design was adopted using questionnaire to obtain data from a sampled population of 368 employees. The generated data were analyse using descriptive and inferential statistics. Results of the study revealed that work environment was not conducive and that it is the major reason for low level of institution effectiveness in the study area. A balance between the two findings above, was that of Eyo (2021) who found that work environment of library personnel is in south-south, Nigeria is moderately conducive.

Pratiwi (2019) investigated the influence of work facilities on employee performance at Regional financial agency secretariat in South Sulawesi. Thirty-five (35) staff responded to the questionnaire. The results of the correlational test revealed that work facilities provided for respondents are machinery, and equipment in their place of work. This expression buttresses the need for adequate work tools for an appreciable level of Job performance. Onuoha and Otuzo (2020) conducted a research on Work environment and Job Satisfaction of Librarians in Private universities in South-east and South-west, Nigeria through a survey method. Questionnaire was used to collect data from 181 librarians. The author used descriptive statistics for the research questions and inferential statistics of Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) to test the hypothesis. Results revealed that work environment of Librarians in those universities libraries were satisfactory in terms of good edifices, neat environment and a good relationship among the respondents. Similar to the above finding is that of Madukoma and Sangosanya (2020) who studied Work environment as Determinants of Job performance of Librarians in the National Library of Nigeria and found that the level of conduciveness of work environment of the library staff generally, can be regarded as conducive by having a grand Mean=2.5 on a four Likert scale. Adenekan and Solomon (2022) investigated work environment, motivation, and service delivery of librarians in Ambrose Alli University (AAU), Ekpoma, Edo State, findings revealed that, the work environment is not conducive.

This is because among all the items of work environment such as amazing work culture, adequate health safety and training, occupation hazard mitigation, employee friendly policies, job security have mean below the bench mark and the cause for the low level of service delivery as revealed in the study.

Kuhaki et al. (2022) research was titled ‘Subjective and objective survey of office lighting: effects on alertness, comfort, satisfaction, and safety life’. The population of the study are Eighty-five (85) staffs. Data were collected through questionnaire. ANOVA used to analyse the collected data. The findings revealed a significant moderate correlation between the independent variable (office layout, furniture, and lighting) and the dependent variable (job performance). Fithri et al. (2019) studied the Impact of Work environment on Employees’ performance in Local Government of Padang city using a sampled population of 384 staff and questionnaire was used to collect the required data. After analysis through Structural Equation Model Partial Least Square (SME-PLS). The results revealed a positive and significance influence of both physical and non-physical work environments on employee performance based on the premise that both the t-statistic of physical work environment and that of a non-physical work environment were greater than the t-table value at 0.05 significance level. Malik et al. (2011) studied work environment and employee performance in Pakistan. Data were collected through the use of questionnaire from 115 respondents and were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The results obtained through Pearson correlation and regression revealed that, there is positive relationship between dimensions of work environment and employee performance especially physical work environment conditions.

Ikonne and Fajoyonmi (2019) carried out study on Work environment and Job Satisfaction on Librarians’ job performance in North-east, Nigeria. The results revealed a no significant relationship between work environment of Librarians and work performance. However, they observed that the work environment of librarian in terms of physical facilities, open communication motivation among others are fairly favorable. Pratiwi (2019) studied the influence of work of work facilities on employee performance at the regional financial management Agency in south Sulawesi, the results of the correlation test analysis revealed that there is significant influence between work environment in-terms of are machinery, equipment, and performance of Respondents. According to Saidi et al. (2019) in a study of the relationship between working environment and employee performance observed that employee performance can be affected by lightings, temperature, noise, office layout and fresh air which are all constituents of physical work environments. Co-workers relation and peers support will motivate a worker to do what is not part of job description as a result of comfortable office environment. In support of the above opinion is that of Madukoma and Sangosanya (2022) in a study of work environment as determinants of job performance of Librarians in the National Library of Nigeria expressed that librarians require conduciveness work environment which includes constant electricity supply, adequate ventilation, and space and friendly environment. In the authors view friendly environment means those social aspects of the work environment like social support, knowledge sharing, communication behaviour and work relation among others.

METHODOLOGY

A survey research design was adopted for this study using 219 library staff that comprised professional and para-professional from six State University libraries in the North-east, Nigeria. A census sampling was used in this study, because, the population is considered by the researcher, not too large to manage. A self-developed questionnaire titled “Questionnaire on Influence of Work environment on Job performance (QWEJP) was used to collect data. The

draft copy of the questionnaire was vetted by experts. The questionnaire is divided into three sections. Section A elicit information on demographic data of the respondents. Section B was on Level of Job performance structured in a 5point Likert format Very low level (VLL), Low level (LL), Moderate level (ML), High level (HL), and very High level (VHL). Section C was on the conduciveness of work environment of Library staff in state university libraries, north-east, Nigeria is also structured on a 5point Likert scale sing Strongly disagree (SD)=1, Disagree (D)=2, Undecided (UD)=3, Agree (A)=4 and Strongly Agree (SA)=5. Descriptive statistics of frequency count, percentages, and mean score was used to answer the two research questions. The decision guide for interpreting the research answers was reached from the summary or average scores of the frequency, percentages and the mean. The bench mark mean on a five-point Likert scale is 3.0. Hence, the interpretation of the mean scores is that, a mean equals 1.0-2.4 is Low level, 2.5-3.4 is moderate level, and 3.5-5.0 is high level. While, for the conduciveness of work environment the interpretation is: 1.0-2.4 is a low conduciveness, 2.5-3.4, moderate conduciveness, and 3.5-5.0 is high conduciveness. Inferential statistics of linear regression was employed to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS AND INTERPRETATION

A total of 209 copies of questionnaire were distributed to the respondents in the six State University libraries. Out of this number, 189 were retrieved and 168 found suitable for analysis. Thereby achieving a response rate of 80.3%.

Table 1: Level of Job Performance of the Respondents

S/N	Job Performance of librarians	VLL	LL	ML	HL	VHL	\bar{X}	Std
1	I process and classify library resources accurately	26 (15.5)	27 (16.1)	56 (33.3)	37 (22.0)	22 (13.1)	3.01	1.238
2	I ensure timely and efficient access to physical and digital resources	19 (11.3)	33 (19.6)	57 (33.9)	47 (28.0)	12 (7.1)	3.00	1.105
3	I train users for promoting information literacy and access tools	20 (11.9)	28 (16.7)	51 (30.4)	44 (26.2)	25 (14.8)	3.15	1.219
4	I support research and academic engagement through expert assistance	22 (13.1)	39 (23.2)	53 (31.5)	36 (21.4)	18 (10.7)	2.93	1.184
5	I maintain technological, digital, and infrastructural systems	22 (13.1)	35 (20.8)	54 (32.1)	36 (21.4)	21 (12.5)	2.99	1.206
6	I manage acquisitions, collections, and policies professionally	22 (13.1)	27 (16.1)	38 (22.6)	46 (27.4)	35 (20.8)	3.27	1.315
	Average mean						3.06	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 1 above presents the surveyed data from 168 library staff in state university libraries, north-east, Nigeria on the level of job performance. Item number one which is 'I process and classify library resources accurately' is disagreed by 19%, undecided by 4.2% and agreed by 76.7% respondents. The item recorded a mean=3.02. Item number two is disagreed by 8.4%, undecided by 2.4%, agreed by 89.2% respondents. The item recorded a mean=3.00. Item three

was disagreed by 17.9%, undecided by 6.0%, agreed by 76.1% the respondents, and recorded the lowest mean =2.93 among all the means, but indicates moderate performance based on the decision guide. Furthermore, item number four was disagreed by 36.3%, undecided by 31.5 %, agreed by 32.1% respondents, and recorded a mean=2.93. Item number five was disagreed by 33.9%, undecided by 32.1%, agreed by 33.9% respondents, and recorded a lowest mean=2.99. Finally item number 6 was disagreed by 29.2%, undecided by 22.6%, agreed by 48.2% respondents, and recorded a mean=3.27 being the highest mean. This implies that the respondents are effective in managing acquisitions, collections, and policies professionally. The Grand mean score of 3.06 indicates an overall moderate level of job performance by the respondents based on the decision guide of the study.

Table 2: Conduciveness of the Work Environment of the Respondents

S/N	Work environment	SD (f/)	D	U	A	SA	x	Std.
1	The library environment has adequate ventilation which makes me feel comfortable for job performance	13 (7.7)	19 (11.3)	7 (4.2)	72 (42.8)	57 (33.9)	3.84	1.230
2	My library environment is quiet enough to allow concentration for job performance.	6 (3.6)	8 (4.8)	4 (2.4)	85 (50.6)	65 (38.5)	4.16	0.950
3	My office furniture is comfortable enough that I can work without discomfort.	10 (6.0)	20 (11.9)	10 (6.0)	72 (42.9)	56 (33.2)	3.86	1.180
4	Work spaces in our library are adequate.	11 (6.5)	17.3 (29)	7.7 (13)	41.1 (69)	27.4 (46)	3.65	1.233
5	My library working environment lighting is dull (not appropriate for reading and seeing).	27 (16.1)	44 (26.2)	16 (9.5)	54 (32.1)	27 (16.1)	3.06	1.370
6	Work tools (selection tools, cataloguing tools, stationaries, etc.) are current and adequately provided.	11 (6.5)	15 (8.9)	23 (13.7)	74 (44.0)	45 (26.8)	3.76	1.140
7	Flexible communication helps in clearly specifying task-related goals for good performance.	6 (3.6)	14 (8.3)	17 (10.1)	97 (57.7)	34 (20.2)	3.83	0.966
8	Knowledge sharing in the library is adequately done to reduce uncertainty.	10 (6.0)	15 (8.9)	10 (6.0)	87 (51.7)	46 (27.4)	3.86	1.101
9	I am being socially supported in terms of tasks in my library.	(5) (3.0)	11 (6.5)	19 (11.3)	83 (49.4)	50 (29.8)	3.96	0.972
10	I relate harmoniously with other employees on a formal and informal level.	6 (3.6)	8 (4.8)	18 (10.6)	90 (53.6)	46 (27.4)	3.96	0.947
	Grand mean						3.79	

Sources: Field Survey 2025

Table 2 above provided the responses of the Respondents on the aspects of their work environment on a 5-point Likert scale. The first item on the table on work environment ‘library environment with adequate ventilation that is comfortable for job performance, has 19% of the

responses for disagree, 4.2% undecided, 76.8% agreed and a mean=3.84. Item number 2 has 8.4% responses for disagree, 2.4% for undecided, 89.2% for agreed and a mean score=4.16. This is highest mean among all means. This reflects strong agreement, that the library’s quiet environment supports concentration. Item number 3 has 17.9% response for disagree, 6.0% for undecided, while 75.1% were for agree and recorded a mean= 3.86. This suggest that, furniture is comfortable to supporting work without physical discomfort. Item 4 showed that, 23.8 % responses were for disagree, 7.7% for undecided, and 68.5 % for agree. The statement has a mean score = 3.65. This mean score, is the second-lowest, but is above the mean bench mark, thus, indicating an agreement with the item. .Item number 5 has 42.3% responses for disagree, 9.5% for undecided 48.2%, for agree, and a mean =3.06. The mean of 3.06, the lowest among all mean, but is suggesting a high level of agreement with the item.

Furthermore, item number 6 has 15.4% responses for disagree, 13.7% for undecided, 70.8% for agree and a mean score = 3.76. Since the mean is above the bench mark, work tools (selection tools, cataloguing tools, stationaries, etc.) being current and adequately provided are agreed to be satisfactory. Item number 7 has 11.9% for disagree, 10.1% for undecided, while, 77.9% for agree, and recorded a mean score=3.83. Item number 8 has 14.9% responses for disagree, 6.0% for undecided, 79.1% for agree, and a mean = 3.86. Item number 9 has 9.5% for disagree, 11.3% for undecided, 79.2% for agree, with a mean score=3.96 .The mean of 3.96, is the highest. Finally, item 10 harmonious relationship with other employees on a formal and informal level showed the responses that 8.4% disagreed, 10.6% undecided, 81% agreed, with a mean score of 3.96 The mean score of 3.96, is the second highest, implying that the respondents having a level of harmonious work relation. The grand mean score is 3.79, going by the decision guide of study, indicated a high level of conduciveness of the work environment of the respondents.

Table 3: Model Summary of Simple linear Regression Analysis on the Influence of Work Environment on Job Performance of the Respondents.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.357a	.128	.122	.743

a. Predictors: (Constant), Work Environment

The results in table 3 displayed that R=.357, R²= .128, Adj R²= .122. The Adj R²= .122 implies that, the variance of library staff job performance in state university libraries could be attributed to the 12.2% contribution of work environment and that other factors contribute 87.2% in explaining the job performance of library staff in state university libraries, north-east, Nigeria.

Table 4 Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) of the Linear Regression on the Non-influence of Work Environment on Job Performance of the Respondents

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	13.402	1	13.402	24.297	.000b
	Residual	91.566	166	.552		
	Total	104.968	167			

a. Dependent Variable: Job Performance
 b. Predictors: (Constant), Work Environment

The ANOVA is displayed in table 4 above, and the results revealed that F-statistic =24.297, p < 0.001. Since P< .000) is less than p<.05), this implies that the hypothesis which state ‘there

is no significant influence of work environment on job performance of library staff in state university libraries, north-east, Nigeria’ was rejected and replaced with the alternate one.

Table 5: Coefficients of the Correlation between Work environment and Job Performance of the Respondents.

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	1.330	.356		3.737	.000
Work Environment	.456	.093	.357	4.929	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Job Performance

The coefficients is displayed in table 5 above. The work environment’s coefficient (B = 0.456, p =0.000 (p < 0.05). The calculated significance level of 0.000 (p < 0.05). This shows that the independent variable (work environment) has a statistically significant influence of the on the dependent variable (job performance). The null hypothesis that there is no significant influence of work environment on job performance of library staff is rejected and replaced with the alternate one.

SUMMARY OF THE FINDINGS

1. The level of job performance among library staff in state university libraries, north-east, Nigeria is moderate.
2. The work environment of library staff in the state university libraries, north-east, Nigeria is very conducive.
3. There is significant influence of work environment on library staff job performance in state university libraries, north-east, Nigeria.

DISCUSSION

The study investigated the influence of work environment on library staff job performance of in the State university libraries, north-east, Nigeria. The finding on research question revealed a moderate level of job performance among the Respondents. The finding of this study is in agreement with Verma and Singh (2019) study on level of Job Performance of Library professionals in University Libraries in Varanasi India who found out an average level of Job performance among the library professionals. In contrast to the finding, is that of Fabunmi et al. (2023) and Ikonne and Fajoyonmi (2019) studies in which a low level of job performance was revealed. On the other hand, Eyo (2021) study revealed a high level of job performance among the library personnel in the area under study.

The finding on research question two revealed a high level of conduciveness of work environment of the Respondents. This finding is in agreement with Madukoma and Sangosanya (2020)’s findings in a study of Work environment as determinants of Job performance of Librarians in the National Library of Nigeria which revealed a high conducive level of work environment of the library staff generally. However, the finding is in contrasts with that of Adenekan and Solomon (2022) which revealed an unconducive work environment in the study area. This may be the cause of the low level of service delivery as reported in their study. In order to improve employees’ performance, organization should provide facilities to support completion of work. These facilities and infrastructures are adequate tools, ICT

infrastructures, and absent of pressure for a good level of job performance. Contributing on what it meant by conducive work environment, Adetayo et al. (2023), hold the opinion that, an office environment with pleasant settings in terms of temperature and fresh air, comfortable office, a clean and quite environment, adequate space, good lighting, e.t.c.

The null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant influence of work environment on job performance of library staff in state university libraries, north-east, Nigeria, was rejected. This is because, the analysis of the simple linear regression indicated that work environment significantly influenced job performance. The calculated significance level of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$) indicates that the regression model is statistically significant, rejecting the null hypothesis that the work environment has no influence on job performance and replacing it with an alternate one. This finding supported the findings of Fithri et al. (2019) that, there is a positive and significance influence of both physical and non-physical work environments on employee performance. On a similar note, the finding in this study is in agreement with the findings of Malik et al. (2011) study which revealed a positive relationship between dimensions of work environment and employee performance, especially, the physical work environment performance. Furthermore, finding also, corroborated that of Hamidi et al. (2020) that there is moderate relationship between Physical work environment and employee's performance. Contrary to this research finding, is that of Ikonne and Fajoyonmi (2019). Their results indicated that there is no significant relationship between work environment and Librarians' work performance.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The study, therefore, recommends that:

1. The library administration should prioritize enhancing staff performance by addressing key factors that influence their effectiveness.
2. The library Administration in the study area should endeavour to sustain the high level of conduciveness of work environment.
3. To increase the influence of work environment on job performance, the libraries' administration under study should continue to appreciate the fact that, a conducive work environment is vital for effective job performance of the library staff.

CONCLUSION.

Going by the results of the study, it can be concluded that, the level of library staff job performance in the state University libraries northeast, Nigeria, has been ascertained and that conducive work environment contributes to an improvement of level of job performance of library in State university libraries North-east, Nigeria. However, there is need for an investigation to unravel the other factors that influence the library staff job performance apart from work environment.

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